

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for providing a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.N.) and also to Prof. H.L. Bhatnagar, Head of the Chemistry Department for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. S. ARORA (Miss), H. L. KALRA, S. N. DUBEY and D. M. PURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 445.
2. G. B. WENGERT, R. C. WALKER and V. A. STANGER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 1930.
3. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
4. J. BJERRUM, 'Metal amine formation in aqueous solution', Haase and Son, 1941.
5. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
7. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 327.
8. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, 'Instability constants of complex compounds', Van Nostrand, New York, 1960, p. 59.

Studies on Se(IV) and Te(IV) Dithiocarbamates

NEPAL SINGH, (Miss) KALPANA RASTOGI,
V. K. MAHESHWARI and B. D. KANSAL,

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad.

Manuscript received 30 May 1979, revised 8 January 1980,
accepted 31 March 1980

A perusal of literature shows that scarcely attempts have been made earlier for the study of the aforesaid metal dithiocarbamates¹⁻³. In continuation of our work on Tellurium(IV)⁴ here we report infra-red and thermogravimetric measurements of Se(IV) and Te(IV) complexes of morpholine, piperidine and pyrrolidine dithiocarbamates.

Experimental

Potassium salts of the dithiocarbamates were prepared according to the procedure reported in the literature⁵. The solution of selenium dioxide and potassium tellurite was prepared in distilled water.

Preparation of the Complexes (General Method) :

To a solution of metal(IV) ions (0.1M) in water (20 ml.) was added with stirring the solution (0.1M) of

the potassium salt of the reagent in water (100 ml.). The precipitate was digested on steam-bath for 10 minutes. The complex was filtered, washed with water, finally with ether and dried at 110°-120°.

Results and Discussion

The tellurium(IV) complexes start to lose weight (moisture) at around 90° and completed at 100°. The anhydrous dithiocarbamates decompose sharply at temperature ranging 160-260° [Te(mdtc)₄], 158-250° [Te(pipdtc)₄], and 126-290° [Te(pydtc)₄]. The organic matter completely oxidised at the highest temperature of the aforesaid ranges thereafter a stable region ranging 260-340°, 250-400°, and 290-360°, respectively. In these ranges the formation of tellurium sulphide is concluded which finally oxidised to tellurium oxide. The % of loss in weight observed for different products formed during the heating almost coincide with the % of loss in weight calculated. The DTA confirm the results obtained from TGA

The selenium complexes become anhydrous after losing their moisture around 60°. The decomposition of selenium dithiocarbamates of morpholine, piperidine and pyrrolidine start at 150°, 150° and 130° and completed at 280°, 260° and 300° respectively, thereafter a stable region upto 300°, 320° and 400° which is due to the formation of selenium sulphide. The final product of oxidation is selenium oxide. The DTA supports the observation of TGA.

Results of the TGA curves of the complexes (heating rate 5° min⁻¹) indicate that the complexes of morpholine and piperidine dithiocarbamates with the aforesaid ions are thermally more stable than the pyrrolidine dithiocarbamates. The temperatures at which the complex starts decomposition are lower in case of Se(IV) complexes than the Te(IV) complexes. The rigid morpholine ring to release the electron might be a cause of higher decomposition temperature than the piperidine and pyrrolidine dithiocarbamates complexes.

The assignment for the C-N and C-S stretching frequencies for the complexes are listed in Table-1. The bands in the region 1000-990 cm⁻¹ for the latter and 1480-1470 cm⁻¹ for the former. The C-N mode for diethyl-dithiocarbamate is at 1477 cm⁻¹ compared to 1438 cm⁻¹ - 1445 cm⁻¹ for aforesaid dithiocarbamates. This suggest that there is less double bond character in carbon-nitrogen bond. In all the complexes the ligand shows a bidentate nature. It has been reported earlier that complexes having bidentate R₂NCS₂ group exhibit a single ν(C-N) and a ν(C-S)

TABLE I

S.No.	Compound	Colour	Elemental analysis Found (Calc.)			I.R. Spectra		pH for quantitative precipitation
			C%	H%	N%	C-N cm ⁻¹	C-S cm ⁻¹	
1.	(MDTC).K	White	29.31 (29.82)	3.80 (4.00)	6.95 (6.95)	1442	990	—
2.	(pipDTC).K	White	35.92 (36.14)	4.91 (5.05)	6.89 (7.02)	1445	990	—
3.	(pyDTC).K	White	32.39 (32.39)	4.30 (4.35)	7.48 (7.55)	1438	987	—
4.	(MDTC) ₄ Te	Yellow	30.95 (30.93)	4.13 (4.15)	7.08 (7.21)	1480	1000	3.5–6.5
5.	(pipDTC) ₄ Te	Yellow	37.30 (37.49)	5.19 (5.24)	7.05 (7.28)	1480	1000	3.5–6.0
6.	(pyDTC) ₄ Te	Redish Yellow	33.40 (33.79)	4.27 (4.52)	7.73 (7.86)	1470	995	3.5=6.0
7.	(MDTC) ₄ Se	Light Yellow	32.88 (33.00)	4.17 (4.43)	7.57 (7.69)	1480	980	3.0–5.0
8.	(pipDTC) ₄ Se	Yellow	40.0 (40.03)	5.67 (5.59)	7.48 (7.78)	1480	1000	3.0–5.0
9.	(pyDTC) ₄ Se	Yellow	36.99 (36.17)	4.52 (4.85)	8.51 (8.43)	1475	1000	3.0–5.0

absorptions⁶, whereas those containing monodentates R₂NC(S)S group show doublets for the two modes of vibrations⁷.

References

1. H. BODE, *Z. Analyst Chem.*, 1954, 143, 182.
2. G. ST. NIKOLOV, N. JORDONOV and I. J. HAVEZOV, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 105.
3. P. PORT, T. TARANTELLI, L. GASTALDI and C. FURLANI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1971, 5, 616.
4. N. SINGH, R. KUMAR and R. C. AGARWAL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1977, 46, 851.
5. G. MARCOFRIGIANO, G. C. PELLACANI, C. PRETI and G. TOSI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1975, 48, 1018.
6. F. BONATI and RUGO, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1967, 10, 257.
7. E. C. ALYES, B. S. RAMASWAMI, A. N. BHAT and P. C. RAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 9, 399.

Studies on the Complexes of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) with Benzamidothiosemicarbazide

M. N. ANSARI, M. C. JAIN and WAHID U. MALIK*

Department of Chemistry, S. D. College,
Muzaffarnagar-251 001, U. P.

Manuscript received 24 August 1978, revised 30 November 1979,
accepted 31 March 1980

THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (NH₂CS NH NH₂) and its N-amino derivative (NH₂-NH-CS NH NH₂) thiocarbonylhydrazide, have long been known to possess biochemical and pharmacological¹ including

*Prof. Wahid U. Malik, Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee.

anticarcinogenic², antibacterial and fungicidal³ properties. They have also been used in the industry⁴. Campbell and Grzeskowiak⁵ prepared two series of Cu(II) complexes of thiosemicarbazide and elucidated their structure employing ultraviolet and visible spectroscopic techniques. Ajayi *et al.*⁶ reported interaction of Pb(II) with NH₂C(X)NH NH₂ (X=O, S, Se) and calculated stability constant by polarographic method. Stability constant and heat of formation of Hg(II) complex of thiosemicarbazide were determined by Goddard and co-workers⁷.

In the present communication the results of our studies on the composition and structural characteristics of benzamidothiosemicarbazide (abbreviated as BTSC) and Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) have been reported.

Experimental

Benamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) was prepared by the method described by Verma⁸ and its solution prepared by dissolving weighed amounts in 80 : 20 ethyl alcohol : water mixture. Fresh solution of BTSC was always used. Stock solutions of copper acetate, mercuric chloride, and lead acetate were prepared by dissolving these salts (B. D. H. 'AR' grade) in doubly distilled air free water. The strengths of these solutions were determined by the usual methods.

Conductometric titrations of BTSC against Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) were carried out to determine the complexes. A series of solutions keeping the concentration constant and varying the metal (direct titration) and vice-versa (reverse titration) were prepared keeping the volume constant in each case. The plots of conduc-